

A Bibliometric Analysis of Global Trends in Vegan-Related Research

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Abstract

This study is the first bibliometric analysis of vegan-related research. This article aims to identify and organize fundamental and influential works across several decades in order to gain insight into global trends in vegan-related research. We searched the Scopus database and included all relevant articles published from 1960 (inception) to 2020. We limited our search to English language articles containing the terms “vegan,” “vegans,” or “veganism” in the title or abstract. We included all types of articles that were published in journals. We conducted a bibliometric analysis with the open-source R programming software-based Bibliometrix package. There were a total of 1440 relevant articles published in 664 journals over a span of 60 years. The first article was published in 1962. The average publication rate was 9.68 articles per year. The top journal was *Nutrients* with total publication of 85 (5.9%) articles and 924 total citations. The United States was the leading country with 471 articles and the University of Oxford was the most prolific institution with 59 articles. There was a total of 4586 authors with an average of 28 citations per article. McCarty from the United States was the leading author. The keyword “vegan” was the most used term with 411 occurrences, widely published in *Nutrients* by the United States authors. We conclude that the United States is the leading country in the field of vegan-related research and, if the trajectory we noted continues, the global trend in vegan-related research is likely to continue surging.

Keywords: Bibliometric; Vegan; Analysis; Research; Trend

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Introduction

In 1962, the *Oxford Illustrated Dictionary* introduced the word “vegan” meaning “a vegetarian who eats no butter, eggs, cheese, or milk.”¹ In 1994, the Vegan Society from the United Kingdom declared every November 1 as World Vegan Day and subsequently every November as World Vegan Month.²

Veganism is “a philosophy and way of living which seeks to exclude—as far as is possible and practicable—all forms of exploitation of, and cruelty to, animals for food, clothing or any other purpose; and by extension, promotes the development and use of animal-free alternatives for the benefit of animals, humans and the environment.”³ A person who adopts that philosophy and practices such a lifestyle is known as a vegan.³ A “vegan diet” is defined for dietary purposes as the practice of avoiding all products derived from animals.³ A vegan diet is different from other diets, such as a vegetarian diet. A vegetarian diet predominantly consists of plants but may contain dairy, eggs, honey, and/or other animal-derived products.⁴ Therefore, someone may become a vegetarian, consuming a diet primarily from plant sources, but not be a vegan since veganism, as the above definition indicates, allows for no animal-derived substances and goes well beyond diet alone.

In a survey conducted in 2018 across 28 countries, 3% of the global adult population identified as vegan.⁵ Also in 2018, a Gallup poll revealed that there were about 7.5 million adult vegans in the United States.⁶ A joint survey conducted in 2019 showed that the number of vegan adults in the United Kingdom increased from 150,000 (0.25% of the population) in 2014 to 600,000 (1.16% of the population).⁷ According to an Acumen Research and Consulting report, the global vegan food market is expected to reach around \$24.3 billion by 2026 and will rise at a notable compound annual growth rate of around 9.1% from 2019 to 2026.⁸ Motif, a food technology company, was launched in 2019 after raising \$90 million in investment for a vegan meat start-up. Part of the funding came from Breakthrough Energy Ventures, a fund that involves billionaires including Amazon’s Jeff Bezos, Microsoft’s Bill Gates, and Virgin’s Richard Branson.⁹

There have also been ground-breaking studies about the positive health effects of a vegan diet. A vegan diet was associated with a substantial reduction in overall cancer incidence (-15%).¹⁰ In comparison to omnivores, vegans had lower levels of C-reactive protein (mean difference -0.54 mg/L) and, as a result, a reduced risk of chronic disease.¹¹ A vegan diet also improved glycemic control in patients with type 2 diabetes.¹² Sports performances, especially among endurance athletes, also benefited from a vegan diet due to reduction in oxidative stress, improved vascular flow, and tissue oxygenation.¹³

A study using Google Trends to explore global popularity—as defined by the number of searches on vegan-related terms as a fraction of total searches in a given country of various search categories such as veganism, which includes vegan-related queries in any language—showed that the popularity of veganism was at an all-time high in 2020. Vegan-related queries were most popular in the United Kingdom, Australia, Israel, Austria, and New Zealand.¹⁴ There was also increased participation in the Veganuary campaign in 2021. Veganuary is the biggest vegan campaign in the world. It encourages people to go vegan for the month of January and beyond. More than 500,000 people from all over the world signed up for the annual challenge, breaking the previous record by about 100,000 people.¹⁵ Advocacy for plant-based diets and veganism by celebrities and athletes such as Joaquin Phoenix and Lewis Hamilton are also causing more mainstream visibility. There is also a rise in the number of documentary films, such as *Seaspiracy* and *The Game Changers*, that center around veganism.¹⁶

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Patient consent

This study does not involve human subjects; therefore, informed consent was not required.

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Conflicts of interest

None

Ethics approval

The authors used only previously published data; thus, ethical approval was not sought.

With the increasing interest in veganism worldwide, we sought to explore whether a similar trend has occurred in scientific literature. Our unique approach involved a novel study of the material. This article aims to identify and organize fundamental and influential works across several decades to gain insight into global trends in vegan-related research (VRR). In order to achieve that, we performed a bibliometric analysis of research articles that were published over a span of 60 years in order to demonstrate general research patterns of VRR.

Methods

This study was registered with the local National Medical Research Register (NMRR-21-328-59004).

Literature Search

We searched the Scopus database in March 2021 and included all relevant articles published from 1960 (inception) to 2020. Scopus was selected because it is a well-known index that covers a large number of peer-reviewed publications and offers reliable bibliographic information.^{17,18} We limited our search to English language articles containing the terms “vegan,” “vegans,” or “veganism” in the title or abstract. Study authors were contacted for full articles or clarification where necessary.

Study Selection

All articles obtained were screened by title and abstract independently by 3 investigators. Full-text articles were retrieved and reviewed independently by the same investigators to assess eligibility. Any disagreements were resolved by consensus. The authors included all types of journal articles. Studies were excluded if they a) were not within the study period (1960–2020), b) were non-journal articles (e.g., book), c) resulted from a search term homonym (words that have identical spelling and pronunciation, but different meanings (e.g., VEGAN, a package of R functions for community ecology), d) were not in context (e.g., only mentioned the word vegan in the abstract but the article itself was not related to vegan, vegans, or veganism), e) were duplicates, or f) contained no relevant bibliometric data.

Bibliometric Analysis

A bibliometric analysis is a methodical approach using statistical and quantitative analysis based on the outputs of a scholarly literature database in order to understand global research patterns in a particular field. A bibliometric analysis mainly intends to address the most recent developments, problems, and future directions of a particular subject. Bibliometric review offers a more objective and reliable approach, as well as the possibility of establishing a systematic, transparent, and reproducible review process.¹⁹⁻²¹

We performed bibliometric analysis to show a) research interest in publication output and trend, b) preferred or top journals for publication of research, c) countries with the most research interest, d) top institutions/organizations, e) leading authors, and f) commonly used author keywords. We conducted bibliometric and network analysis with the open-source R programming software-based Bibliometrix package.²¹

Results and Discussion

Search Results

Figure 1 shows the literature search and selection process. Initially, we identified a total of 2304 studies. After culling the list based on the inclusion criteria, we obtained 1528 studies. We then screened those studies for relevance to the research theme and excluded 88 irrelevant articles. A total of 1440 studies met the eligibility criteria and were

included in the bibliometric analysis. The oldest article was dated 1962 and the latest was dated 2020.

Figure 1: Flow diagram of the literature screening process

Bibliometric Analysis and Findings

Publication Output and Trend

There was a total of 1440 relevant articles published in 664 journals over a span of 60 years (Figure 2). The first article was published in 1962 and the average publication rate for all journals was 9.68 articles per year. The number of publications, starting with one article in 1962, increased steadily over the years. There was a notable spike after 2012 with an annual growth rate of 54%, reaching a peak of 258 articles in 2020. The average annual growth rate over the entire period was 27%. Based on the trend observed up to 2020, the number of publications in VRR will likely continue to rise and reach a new peak in 2021. Nearly half (43.6%) of the articles are open access journals and the content of the articles is freely available on the websites of the various journals.

Figure 2: The annual and cumulative numbers of research articles on VRR indexed in Scopus from 1962 to 2020

Top Journals and Articles

We identified the top 10 most prolific journals, all of which came from 6 publishers (Table 1). The journal with the highest number of articles was published by the Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute. The publisher of the second most prolific journal was the American Society for Clinical Nutrition, and Elsevier published the third journal in this ranking. There were 3 journals from Elsevier and 2 journals each from Cambridge University Press and Springer Nature.

The most prolific journal was *Nutrients* with 85 articles (5.9%), followed by the *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* with 41 articles (2.8%), *Medical Hypotheses* with 34 articles (2.4%), *Appetite*, 33 articles (2.3%), and the *European Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 27 articles (1.9%). *Nutrients* received the highest number of citations at 924, but the most highly cited article is from the *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* with 215 citations.

CiteScore is a journal evaluation metric that is calculated from the records in the Scopus database. The CiteScore 2019 shows more than half of the top 10 journals are above 5. The *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* has the highest 2019 CiteScore of 12.1. Although *Medical Hypotheses* had the lowest CiteScore in 2019 of 2.2, it provided a significant contribution in VRR and was ranked third. CiteScore may influence the decision of some authors in selecting journals that fit. Besides CiteScore, authors should also consider whether the journal can deliver the work to the right audience and whether it contributes to the progress of the field.

We identified the 2 most cited articles in this study. The first most cited article was titled “Intestinal microbiota metabolism of L-carnitine, a nutrient in red meat, promotes atherosclerosis” published in *Nature Medicine* in 2013²² and the second most cited article was titled “High-level adherence to a Mediterranean diet beneficially impacts the gut microbiota and associated metabolome” published in *Gut* in 2016.²³

Table 1: The top 10 most prolific journals on VRR with their respective most cited article

Rank	Journal	Publisher	Total publication (%)	Total citation	The most cited article (reference)	Times cited
1	<i>Nutrients</i>	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)	85 (5.9%)	924	Comparison of nutritional quality of the vegan, vegetarian, semi-vegetarian, pesco-vegetarian and omnivorous diet ²⁴	118
2	<i>American Journal of Clinical Nutrition</i>	American Society for Clinical Nutrition	41 (2.8%)	384	Systematic review and meta-analysis of different dietary approaches to the management of type 2 diabetes ²⁵	215
3	<i>Medical Hypotheses</i>	Elsevier	34 (2.4%)	97	Vegan proteins may reduce risk of cancer, obesity, and cardiovascular disease by promoting increased glucagon activity ²⁶	15
4	<i>Appetite</i>	Elsevier	33 (2.3%)	211	Attitudes towards following meat, vegetarian and vegan diets: An examination of the role of ambivalence ²⁷	69
5	<i>European Journal of Clinical Nutrition</i>	Springer Nature	27 (1.9%)	176	A vegan or vegetarian diet substantially alters the human colonic faecal microbiota ²⁸	139
6	<i>Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Ethics</i>	Springer Nature	27 (1.9%)	61	The least harm principle may require that humans consume a diet containing large herbivores, not a vegan diet ²⁹	17

Table 1 (continued)

Rank	Journal	Publisher	Total publication (%)	Total citation	The most cited article (reference)	Times cited
7	<i>British Journal of Nutrition</i>	Cambridge University Press	26 (1.8%)	283	Taurine concentrations in the diet, plasma, urine and breast milk of vegans compared with omnivores ³⁰	16
8	<i>Journal of The American Dietetic Association</i>	Elsevier	23 (1.6%)	63	Position of the American Dietetic Association: vegetarian diets ³¹	185
9	<i>PLOS One</i>	Public Library of Science	20 (1.4%)	237	When eating right, is measured wrong! A validation and critical examination of the ORTO-15 questionnaire in German ³²	68
10	<i>Public Health Nutrition</i>	Cambridge University Press	18 (1.3%)	167	EPIC-Oxford: Lifestyle characteristics and nutrient intakes in a cohort of 33 883 meat-eaters and 31 546 non meat-eaters in the UK ³³	114

Leading Countries and Top Institutions/Organizations

Table 2 depicts the top 10 most active countries producing articles on VRR globally. Table 3 depicts the top 10 most active institutions/organizations. The United States was the leading country. Its 471 articles represent about one-third of the total articles. This indicates that the United States is playing a key role in the vegan research field and that may be the reason why it also has the highest adult population of vegans worldwide.⁶ With just under one-half the number of articles of the United States, the United Kingdom is ranked number 2 with 214 articles. Italy, with 118 articles, is in third place. Other than first place (United States), fifth place (Australia), and sixth place (Canada), the top 10 articles are otherwise from European countries. This is an interesting phenomenon and is consistent with a previous study showing Europe as the leading continent in internet vegan searches based on the Google Trends Data.¹⁴ It is noteworthy that VRR is not as popular in other continents, such as Asia and Africa.

Of the top 10 institutions/organizations, 2 were from the United States (Physicians Committee for Responsible Medicine [PCRM] and Pantox Laboratories). With regard to academic institutions, there were 2 from the United Kingdom, 2 from the United States, 2 from Germany, and 1 each from Italy and Finland. The most productive institution/organization is in the United Kingdom (University of Oxford), which, with 59 publications, contributed more than one-fourth of the United Kingdom total. There are 4 divisions in the university: medical sciences; humanities; mathematical, physical, and life sciences; and social sciences.³⁴ The medical sciences division is the largest among the university's 4 academic divisions and produced the most publications with 33 articles. It is also a centre for biomedical and clinical research and education and it is therefore understandable that this particular division is leading the total publications in the university. Loma Linda University came in second with 38 articles. It is worth noting that this university in California is a Seventh-day Adventist university. The university is committed to a mission-focused learning environment through the incorporation of health, science, and faith. The Seventh-day Adventist Church vigorously advocates vegetarianism. The university was founded by the church, so it is natural for the university to also be actively involved in VRR, with the Adventist Health Study being a good example.³⁵ Loma Linda University is followed by George Washington University in Washington, DC with 33 publications. Loma Linda University's school of medicine and health sciences alone contributed 22 articles, as did George Washington University's school of medicine and health sciences. The fourth-ranked institution/organization is PCRM, which is also located in Washington, DC. Physi-

cians Committee for Responsible Medicine, which was established in 1985, is a non-profit organization that promotes preventive medicine, performs clinical research, and supports higher ethical as well as effective research standards. It is committed to protecting, improving, and saving the lives of humans and animals, with a focus on plant-based diets and ethical scientific study that does not use animals.³⁶ Given the mission of this organization, it is not surprising that PCRM is actively involved in VRR.

According to the Times Higher Education World University Rankings 2021, only 2 of the universities that appeared in our results were in the top 100 best universities globally. The University of Oxford was number 1 in the world ranking. King's College London was ranked 35th. This is followed by George Washington University (187th), and Università degli Studi di Torino (401-500th), Itä-Suomen yliopisto (401-500th), Justus-Liebig-Universität Gießen (401-500th), and Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Universität Hannover (501-600th).³⁷ This indicates that vegan-related study is still not mainstream for most of the top universities. However, seeing that the University of Oxford has taken a leading role, VRR may become a more sought-after study domain for top universities in the future.

Table 2: The top 10 most prolific countries in VRR

Rank	Country	Total publication
1	United States	471
2	United Kingdom	214
3	Italy	118
4	Germany	111
5	Australia	75
6	Canada	60
7	Sweden	49
8	France	46
9	Spain	45
10	Netherlands	43

Table 3: The top 10 most prolific institutions/ organizations in VRR

Rank	Institution/Organization	Total publication
1	University of Oxford	59
2	Loma Linda University	38
3	George Washington University	33
4	Physicians Committee for Responsible Medicine	24
5	Pantox Laboratories	22
6	Università degli Studi di Torino	21
7	Itä-Suomen yliopisto	20
8	King's College London	19
9	Justus-Liebig-Universität Gießen	17
10	Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Universität Hannover	15

Leading Authors

There was a total of 4586 authors with an average of 28 citations per article and an average of 3 citations per year per article. Research collaboration is on the rise for many reasons.³⁸ Therefore, a similar trend can be seen in VRR too. Most of the authors (4393, 95.8%) included in the study are from multi-authored articles and 193 (4.2%) are from single-authored articles.

Table 4 showed that the top 10 most prolific authors in VRR are from 3 countries, namely the United States (6 authors), the United Kingdom (3 authors), and Germany (1 author). Apart from being the leading country in overall research, the United States also produced the most leading authors in VRR. The first article was published in 1977 by Sanders.³⁹ Most of the authors were co-authors for their first publication except McCarty. The authorship status of a research paper alone cannot be used to determine its worth. Other considerations, such as the journal's quality and/or the authors' roles, must be considered in order to fully evaluate the work. A co-authored work from a premier journal, for example, could be worth more than a single-authored work from a second-tier journal.

McCarty from the United States is the leading author. He has had 38 articles and 700 citations since 1998. Of the 270 single-authored articles, he contributed about 13% of them. The relative difficulty of being published as a single author is testament to his expertise and knowledge in the field. The second top author is Barnard from PCRM in the United States with 32 articles and 1442 citations. The third and fourth top authors are both from the University of Oxford. Each of them contributed the greatest number of citations among the top authors with 2306 for Key and 2105 for Appleby. Among the top 10 leading authors in VRR, both Key and Appleby also provided the most remarkable h-indexes: 125 and 78, respectively. The h-index is an author-level metric that assesses the output of articles and the citations associated with those articles. It is linked to obvious measures of achievement, such as winning the Nobel Prize, receiving research fellowships, and holding positions at prestigious universities.⁴⁰

There was already some collaboration among the leading authors in their first articles. This can be seen, for example, between Turner-McGrievy and Barnard⁴¹ as well as between Key and Sanders.⁴² When the topic of interest is similar, it is common to see some research relationship among authors. The collaboration index among the 4586 authors is 3.75. Hence, there is still opportunity for more author collaboration in VRR in the future.

Table 4: The top 10 leading authors in VRR

Rank	Scopus author ID	h-index	Year of 1st article	TP	TC	Current affiliation	Country
1	24435224500	40	1998 ⁴³	38	700	Catalytic Longevity	US
2	7004632410	37	1999 ⁴⁴	32	1442	PCRM	US
3	7102740999	125	1987 ⁴²	31	2306	University of Oxford	UK
4	7006332366	78	2000 ⁴⁵	26	2105	University of Oxford	UK
5	7201612803	65	1993 ⁴⁶	18	1128	Loma Linda University	US
6	6506257255	24	2012 ⁴⁷	18	738	Loma Linda University	US
7	7202485003	56	1977 ³⁹	15	972	King's College London	UK
8	7801439333	29	2004 ⁴¹	15	395	University of South Carolina	US
9	55223847400	43	2003 ⁴⁸	13	275	Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Universität Hannover	Germany
10	47161103600	19	2014 ⁴⁹	13	249	PCRM	US

Author Keywords with Three-fields Plot

Figure 3 depicts the interconnections of the top 10 journals, author keywords, and countries based on a Sankey diagram. We identified that the keyword “vegan” is the most used term with 411 occurrences. The term is widely used in articles published in *Nutrients* by United States authors. Likewise, *Nutrients* and United States authors published a substantial number of studies with the keywords “vegetarian” (328, second), “diet” (294, third), and “nutrition” (168, fourth). The United States was at the top of the list with regard to the rest of the keywords except for those about “vegan diet.” Authors from Italy used the term “vegan diet” most frequently. Among the journals, *Nutrients* produced studies with the widest coverage of the various author keywords. Nevertheless, “veganism” and “vegetarianism” were covered more extensively by the *Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Ethics*. This is probably due to the fact that this journal is more concerned with lifestyle issues, morality of conduct, virtue, etc. than it is about nutrition.

Figure 3: Three-fields plot (sources, keywords, countries)

Limitation

We only included literature from the Scopus database. Future studies that include other databases like the Web of Sciences will be beneficial for a more comprehensive study with bibliometric analysis. Another limitation is that we only considered English language articles that were published in journals. This is due to the fact that the authors are English speakers and needed to review all the literature in order to include those that met the eligibility criteria. Lastly, the results are based solely on bibliometric analysis. We did not consider other factors such as the population of a country, etc. that may affect the results and analysis in this study.

Conclusion

This study was the first bibliometric analysis of VRR that offered a comprehensive overview over a span of 60 years of the productivity and visibility of VRR, and the results

could be used to organize and prioritize future VRR efforts. We conclude that a) the United States is the leading country, b) *Nutrients* is the most prolific journal, c) University of Oxford is the top institution, d) McCarty is the most productive author, and e) “vegan” is the most used term in global trends overall in VRR. Even though VRR may not be as popular as other research domains, the average annual publication growth rate of 27%, the rapid increase in the number of vegans worldwide, and how inquisitive the world is about veganism may signal that VRR will surge and possibly be a much more important research domain in the future.

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